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The Role of Aesthetic and Artistic Culture in the Spiritual Life of Society

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Abstract: *This article covers the role of aesthetic and artistic culture in the spiritual life of the society, the nature of artistic and aesthetic values, the integral reflection of the physical and mental abilities of a person with all their existence and spheres of art, which is one of the main parts of the artistic culture of the society, and its formation as the basis of artistic culture.*

Key words: *aesthetic and artistic culture, spiritual life of society, artistic values, art, aesthetic values, artistic activity, aesthetic need, artistic creativity, education of a well-rounded personality, socio-artistic phenomenon.*

A person's activity of aesthetic-creative mastering of the world directed at achieving certain practical, social goals, his attitude to his subjects serves as an important moral motivation. This attitude takes a leading place in artistic activities that are inextricably linked with professional and amateur forms of artistic creation, artistic design, etc.

Artistic values and their combination occupy an important place in the structure of aesthetic culture. Art, on the one hand, is "formed and developed under the influence of socio-historical events of the period, and on the other hand, reflects national culture and the aesthetic needs of every artist" [1], is the main field of embodying the aesthetic ideal, mastering the essence of social processes, their development serves the purpose of setting trends. Perception of artistic values has a strong ideological-emotional impact and develops a person's ability to esthetically master the world. Art also becomes an important factor of ideological-aesthetic education by holistically reflecting the physical and mental abilities of a person with all their being and spheres.

Since culture is the embodiment of its essential forces and the results of the method of activity in all spheres of human activity, this feature is fully applicable to the economic, political, moral, including the artistic sphere. In other words, artistic culture is a specific type of human activity and a way of embodying his creative potential.

Art is the basis of artistic culture, for centuries it has played the role of an important moral-aesthetic factor as a very subtle, extraordinary phenomenon that attracts a person spiritually and emotionally. As E. Umarov wrote, "art is the things created, brought into existence, created by human labor, intelligence, and consciousness. Art is a creative type of human activity, and each work of art shows the unique talent of a person. And, finally, art is closely connected with human skill."

The artistic culture of the society can be seen in the past, as well as the art values created in the new era, as well as in the way of their assimilation. Artistic culture is an important area of the general aesthetic culture of society and as a socio-spiritual phenomenon that determines its character in many ways, it performs specific functions, has a specific structure, and acquires relative independence. The process of development and spread of artistic culture in society is the essence of art in a broad social sense.

In the analysis of the social functioning of art and the processes related to it, it is necessary to determine the components that make up the artistic activity of the society. These include, firstly, the things-phenomena that have become the object and subject of artistic perception of the existing reality; secondly, it directly concerns the group of creative people, as well as institutions and associations that create and distribute art values. The third component is the set of values created and taken place from the system of socio-aesthetic relations, and the fourth is the art lovers formed under the influence of art, literature, artistic and literary criticism.

In the conditions of building a democratic legal state, the Decrees, Decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers are important because they are aimed at the comprehensive development of artistic and aesthetic culture. Therefore, in the study of the spiritual life of society, the young generation, or individual strata, a comprehensive analysis of artistic culture fulfills a methodological task.

For example, if a particular social group is defined as a component of artistic culture and analyzed philosophically and aesthetically, then the above components should first of all take priority in the study of their role and importance in creating, spreading and mastering art values. From this point of view, it is not for nothing that the role of artistic intellectuals in our republic is given great importance in the spiritual development of the society, education of a well-rounded personality, artistic reflection of historical reality and modern problems. Therefore, art "since time immemorial has been a representative of the people's heart, a herald of truth and justice."

It was mentioned that the fans of art, which is one of the main parts of the artistic culture of the society, can create a certain social environment in its acquisition. Fans as an art category are a complex structure in terms of social status, age and level of training. It is possible for each layer of fans to express their attitude to art based on their place in society, lifestyle, and activities. Priority artistic needs are considered the main factor in the formation of a certain category of fans and in determining its impact on the culture of society.

In this regard, it is appropriate to present the results of some studies related to the issue. According to the results of a sociological survey, the number of people who are interested in classic literature and art samples that artistically reflect national identity, history and national traditions, as well as their buyers, is a minority. According to the results of a survey of bookstore employees, 46% of the bookstores read detective works, 22.4% - fantasy, 17.2% - romance novels, 13.8% - adventures, 10.3% - horror stories. were interested in the existence of literature, only 8.6% of them had a positive reaction to classic works. As a result, 53.5% bought detective works, 24.1% fiction, 20.7% melo-drama, romance works, 12.1% adventures, 5.2% thrillers, and 0 buyers of classic literature. It is not even 01%

Art fans have a special role in the development of the artistic and aesthetic culture of society, therefore, the growth of culture depends on the strength of the relationship between artists and the mass of fans, and on the increasing role of art in the spiritual education of viewers, listeners and readers. On the other hand, people are always interested in works of art and give social evaluation to new works, strengthening the existing dialectical relationship between artists and the evolving needs of society.

The field of artistic culture is such that it includes not only aesthetic culture, but also elements of moral, cognitive, and organizational culture. In addition, in the field of artistic culture, aspects specific to the culture of creative work and the acquisition of artistic values Artistic culture forms the basis of aesthetic culture as a socio-artistic phenomenon that has become the property of the people. Therefore, artistic culture is the field of artistic values that embodies the highest form of aesthetic values.

In some literature, an attempt to illuminate this relationship by describing the relationship between artistic values and aesthetic values, between artistic activity and aesthetic activity is evident. Accordingly, the artistic need is recognized as the perception and creation of works of art, and the aesthetic need is not limited to art in the harmony of natural and social reality, enjoyment of beauty and creation based on the laws of beauty. are also expressed. Not only aesthetic, but also epistemological, organizational needs and abilities of a person are involved in fiction, painting, music, etc.

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It seems that aesthetic culture is not only artistic, but at the same time, it has a broad meaning, as it includes labor activity, life, emotional-emotional attitude to the outside world. Accordingly, the concepts of "aesthetic culture" and "artistic culture" differ from each other in content and volume.

They differ from each other in terms of activities and play different roles in the life of society. We can see this when we compare artistic and aesthetic values. Artistic values are always based on the creation, distribution and assimilation of concrete products of creative activity, while aesthetic values are essentially more general and are distinguished by their uniqueness in the emotional impact of natural phenomena or colorful labor products, and the satisfaction of needs.

The characteristics, type and size, scope and directions of reality expressed in aesthetic values Aesthetic values apply in the process of aesthetic assimilation of reality, are inextricably linked with the activity of the concrete social subject who changes the world and himself according to the standards of beauty. It is possible to talk about the level of development and existence of aesthetic culture only in relation to this concrete social subject.

Thus, the comparative analysis of the concepts of "aesthetic culture" and "artistic culture" allows, on the one hand, to delimit their spheres, and on the other hand, to determine their specific place in the development of the spiritual life of society. "If in other areas the aesthetic component is of secondary importance," writes M. Abdullaev, "in artistic culture it occupies a leading place." The essence of

artistic culture cannot be imagined without aesthetic activity. This applies equally to the subject of activity, to its forms of activity, to the results of activity, and to its object." Therefore, there are no artistic values without aesthetic value. are much wider than those of artistic values. The subject of these values can be the person himself (his external appearance, inner and outer beauty), beautifully created objects, for example, cultural parks, water reservoirs, cities, man-made aesthetic products, labor activities. Natural phenomena (colorful forms, flowers, manifestations of minerals, colorful fauna and flora, beautiful landscapes) also have such characteristics. Philosopher-scientist M. Abdullaev, speaking about the composition of aesthetic culture, emphasizes that it consists of "behavior, work process, aesthetics of interpersonal communication" in a broad sense, and aesthetic values take material form only in activity.

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